

DIFFERENT METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO 1-4 GRADES STUDENTS

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Abstract: The importance of learning English cannot be overstated. English is the most widely used language in the world for trade, commerce, and industry. For the student of today to be prepared for the job opportunities of tomorrow, they must have a strong command of the English language. The ability to listen, read, write, and speak English at a high level will provide the student with many opportunities to advance themselves academically and professionally

Keywords: language, method, message, activities, thinking, skills, young students, education, stage.

1 INTRODUCTION

At the same time, in teaching English to young students, it is possible to increase their interest in the lesson and their knowledge level in a short period of time by using different methods and activities suitable for their level. It is necessary to use mainly interactive methods when teaching 1-4 grades, because if the lesson process is not interesting for them, they will get bored and have various difficulties in learning the language.

Nowadays, all schools have integrated English curriculum and methods for elementary school students. Because children of this age experience an important stage of development. These are the best years for children to learn a second language, their brain activity quickly adapts to such a situation and tries to acquire the language quickly. Children who are learning a second language may have a native pronunciation, but this is also beneficial because it improves their problem-solving skills. When children learn English and know how to use it, they meet new friends and cultures, which contributes to the development of their worldview and world of thinking. Good knowledge of English helps children to overcome difficulties in learning other languages quickly and easily. [3, p. 146].

Student at a young age is not interested in essays; they want more activities. It is not strange that they get bored easily compared to adults. They have a shorter attention span, varying from a quick 3 minutes to 10 minutes. They do not like to sit for a long period; they want something that can amuse them. Teaching English to young learners who have a very little attention span is definitely a hard task to do. Teachers have to be creative in order to attract the attention of their students. Storytelling could be the perfect solution since there are many stories that can entertain the kids and contain a moral message at the same time. Other variations of media such as songs, puppets, and games are also

effective since they can nurture their interest in the lesson. In conclusion, it is a real challenge to get the attention of young learners, but with the right methods, it is definitely possible. [2, p. 272].

Secondly, young learners do not have good memory capability compared to older people. They usually forget the lesson after some time. In teaching English, memory retention is the most important thing since they have to remember the vocabulary and the meaning. Repetition is the only universal way to implant something into memory. But using the same method over and over again is not an effective way since the kids will get bored. The teacher is faced with another challenge to create a learning method that involves a lot of repetition but still can entertain the kids. An example is a game using flashcards where the teacher puts the similar cards facing down and the kids have to find the similar cards by turning them over. When they find two similar cards, they have to remember the vocabulary of one of the cards, and the one who finds the most pairs wins. This method is more effective compared to just asking them to remember the vocabulary, and it can entertain them at the same time.

2 METHODS

Different methods should be used to eliminate such deficiencies in children's education for example:

1. Storytelling: Narrating simple stories with visuals to aid comprehension and vocabulary acquisition.

2. Songs and Chants: Incorporating catchy songs and chants to teach vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation.

3. Interactive Games: Utilizing games like memory matching, bingo, or word puzzles to make learning fun and interactive.

4. Role-play: Encouraging students to act out everyday situations, like ordering food in a restaurant or greeting someone, to practice language in context.

5. Picture Books: Using colorful picture books with simple sentences to introduce new words and concepts.

6. Language Drills: Engaging students in repetitive exercises like call and response or fill-in-the-blank activities to reinforce language patterns.

7. Art and Crafts: Integrating English into art projects, such as making flashcards or creating storybook illustrations.

8. Technology-Assisted Learning: Incorporating educational apps, videos, and interactive websites to reinforce language skills outside of the classroom.

9. Group Activities: Organizing group discussions, collaborative projects, and peer teaching exercises to promote communication and teamwork.

These types of methods are more convenient for both the teacher conducting the lesson and the student learning the language, also ensure that is the lesson processes are interesting. It also helps to increase students' interest in the lesson and their level of knowledge. [4, p. 73].

Any pedagogue should have own teaching methods to help children become good learners, especially when teaching English, they should use different methods to make children interested in the lesson.

Operative Tips for Teaching English to Beginners:

1. Teaching English to young learners or novices is always a challenge. Especially English as a foreign language is taught to groups who are either monolingual or may be multi-lingual but not native speakers. We need to be more careful and need to keep in mind a few things when teaching English to beginners.

2. Keep your instructions clear and straightforward – Always remember while giving instructions to your new batch of students, that it should be simple and broken down into short sentences, it need not be too formal or courteous. If you want to sound polite, simple words such as 'Please' and 'Thank You' will do, because the learners in the early stage will know only a few words of English and too formal language will be overwhelming.

3. Encourage the novices to listen and then speak. You should motivate the students to listen to the pronunciations, pay attention to the grammar, and develop a vocabulary before they start speaking English. However, you will find many of the learners try to begin speaking in the language as soon as the classes commence. But there will be few who would wait. You should smartly plan your lessons so that the beginners are equipped with sufficient English knowledge and can communicate soon.

4. Drilling and repetition – The students need a lot of repetition and drilling to learn sentences carefully. It may seem monotonous but is an efficient method of

teaching. Say the sentence, break it down, go back and forth and repeat it till the new learner understands it and learns it.

5. Avoid metalanguage – Do not use terminologies as the new learners do not know how to use them while communicating. E.g., irregular verbs, the learners are not sure about these or their usage. So it is better to use visual cues for better comprehension. Try to find out how much they have understood by asking relevant questions or asking them to explain again. Do not ask the question, 'Do you understand?'. The learners, when asked this question, maybe reluctant to reply correctly or may even believe that they have understood everything.

6. Keep in mind that the students are fluent in their language – Do not forget that your students, while speaking broken English, will try to think in their language and translate it into English while speaking. Point this out to them, try to teach them to maintain a flow and rhythm, and deal patiently.

7. Do your homework correctly – When starting a new class prepare well with the topic and keep many related activities ready. Plan out clearly how you will introduce the topic, break the ice, and make your students express.

Think of the probable challenges you may face and keep a solution ready. This makes teaching effective and learning fun for new learners.

3 CONCLUSIONS

Teachers are the torchbearers of a civilized society. For ages, teachers have used different methods, approaches, and styles to suit the child's requirements. Teaching English as a second language is a challenge as we can see that for non-native speakers, various methods need to be devised. In India, English teaching is an exciting task, as we are multi-lingual and have a diverse socio-economic background. Still, general thinking identifies the English language as a mark of being literate. So teachers of this century put together all the methods of teaching English to find the best one for our country. Although too much use of visual aids and gamification of education are still not widespread in our country. [5, p. 125].

In summary, teaching English to young learners involves a natural and rapid process of language acquisition. Effective strategies for their language development emphasize immersive, contextual, and interactive learning experiences that mirror how children naturally acquire language. These approaches aim to make the process of teaching English to young learners enjoyable and meaningful, helping them build their English language skills.

It can be summarized that the methodology of teaching children in elementary school should be based on the following principles:

- Learning through communication and communication with people.
- The most individual approach to students, both in terms of presentation of material and in assessment.
- Interesting, useful, fresh and new information as the basis for the lesson.
- Raising awareness and responsibility for their results.
- Integration of a foreign language with other subjects.

Applying the above rules, you will be able to be the most successful teacher.

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